

METATHEATRICALITY IN SAM SHEPARD'S *FOOL FOR LOVE* AND GIRISH KARNAD'S *HAYAVADANA*: OCCIDENTAL AND ORIENTAL PERSPECTIVES

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Sam Shepard (1943-...) and Girish Karnad (1938-...) are known for their penchant for experimentation and innovation among their contemporaries. Though they belong to two different geographical, cultural and social backgrounds, they tried to position themselves in and make their theatrical endeavors relevant to the postmodern societies. In the twentieth century literature, ontologically, the societies, and the relationships and structures in them are considered to be inherently complex, multileveled, diverse and deep. The social relationships and structures are dynamic, full of nuances, multidimensional and multidirectional. To depict this condition in their plays, one of the theatrical devices they employed is metatheatricality. Though their goals are similar, their stylistics of metatheatricality is different because they draw the techniques and devices from different theatrical milieux. While Shepard draws from the western theatrical traditions, Girish Karnad draws from the Indian classical theater- Sanskrit theater and folk theaters of India such as *Yakshagana*. This paper explores the metatheatricality in Sam Shepard's *Fool For Love* (1984) and Girish Karnad's *Hayavadana* (1975). Further, the techniques employed by these playwrights are compared to and contrasted with one another.

Keywords: Metatheatricality, Postmodern societies, Oriental, Occidental, Theatrical devices.

Introduction

Metatheatricality is a manifestation of theatre's self-reflexivity to the audience. It reveals itself through a layered dramatic performance. This self-reflexivity is inherent to the structure of the play itself. Metatheatricality opens up a vast scope for exploration of alternative versions of reality. When theatricality represents a reality, the metatheatricality allows multi-layered and multi-dimensional realities. It throws a challenge to the assumptions of reality with which the audience perceive a dramatic performance.

Lionel Abel who coined the term 'metatheatre' considers it as a technique that reflects the world as an extension of human consciousness, not accepting prescribed societal norms but allowing for more imaginative variations or a possible social change (183). Further, Richard Hornby in his book, 'Drama, Metadrama and Perception' explores five distinct techniques in metatheatre. He includes formative items such as play within a play, ceremony within a play, role playing within a play, reference to reality and self-reference of the drama.

Historicity

The first example that strikes to one who thinks of metatheatricality is Shakespeare's Hamlet. Shakespeare, the master dramatist has set a bench mark of exploring metatheatricality in a play through

his famous play within a play episode in Hamlet. Through this he creates an on stage microcosm to the play itself. Though there are instances of metatheatricality prior to Shakespeare, the play within the play in Hamlet became a bench mark_for the western dramatic tradition. It has been acknowledged that western dramatic tradition has its roots in Greek drama. Even in the case of play within a play, one can see its prototype in the Greek dramatic tradition in the form of religious rituals. Nellhaus opines that ‘for ancient Greek religious ritual was a historical form that emerged from a set of material and social conditions, most notably the societies’ dependence upon oral culture and hence upon embodied memory (25).

As the societies are advancing, getting more complex, and imbibed with nuance, theatricality which basically functions as a representation or reflection of society in all its form had to come up with devices that are metatheatrical to accommodate, embody and manifest the dynamics and structures of outside world. Nellhaus, quoting Lionel Abel, ‘metatheatre’ is historically coterminous with modern, possessive, self-willed individualism a crucial aspects of western culture since late 16th century (5).

Discussing the historicity of metatheatricality, Nellhaus classifies it into three phases in the English dramatic tradition.

- i) During the 16th century as an inner play (play within a play) serving as a stratagem or a game as in the cases in the Spanish Tragedy and Hamlet.
- ii) In the late 18th century the artist as a man, his personality for its own sake, becomes the focus of interest in the plays concerned with the theatre.
- iii) In the late 19th century the play is intended not to effect but to affect, not to implement an action but to express a being (5)

Many modernist and postmodernist playwrights such as Brecht, Pirandello, Ienesco, Ibsen, Genet have explored metatheatricality in their plays. In continuation of this tradition, Sam Shephard had exploited metatheatricality into new horizons. The character of ‘The Old Man’ in *Fool For Love* is truly a metatheatrical character by every sense. Etymologically ‘meta,’ a Greek prefix in origin, means ‘beyond,’ ‘after,’ ‘with,’ ‘adjacent,’ ‘self,’ etc. The Old Man’s character itself is coterminous with the term ‘meta’. Referring to the character of Don Quixote, Lionel Abel says that he looks for a situation he wants to be part of, not waiting for life, but replacing reality with imagination when the world is lacking in his desire (139).

Sam Shepard’s Metatheatrical Exploits: Occidental Dramatic Tradition

Sam Shepard makes use of metatheatrical characters in his plays. Especially, in *Fool for Love*, he exploits the metatheatrical character skillfully. The Old Man who sits in the rocker on one side of the stage exists only in the mind of Eddie. Though the Old Man speaks both to Eddie and May, only Eddie recognizes him where as May does not. There exixts multiple planes of reality at the same time and space. Multiple planes of reality converge or superimpose one another as a result a unique multilayered and structured reality is emerged. For May only Eddie exists on the stage. For Eddie, May and The Old Man exist but at different planes. For The Old Man both Eddie and May exist, for him both of them occupy same time and space but represent two different versions- a conflict that exists in The Old Man’s mind. For audience, different planes of reality exist-The Old Man on one plane; The Old Man and Eddie on another plane; Eddie and May on yet another plane. All these planes have distinct features of their own.

Throughout the play, Old Man intervenes in the action for six times. At first, he interacts with Eddie. He shows Eddie an imaginary picture on the wall and asks whether he sees it or not. Eddie says, ‘yes.’ The Old Man says that the picture is of Barbara Mandrell. The Old Man tells Eddie, that in fact he did not marry her. However, he claims that he married to her in his mind. When Eddie says that he believes what the Old Man says, The Old Man says, ‘Good. I’m glad we have an understanding’. (*Fool For Love*, 27)

This instance indicates to the audience that both The Old Man and Eddie are connected not at physical level but at metaphysical level. Both of them see an imaginary picture, and have a common understanding though they knew that it is not a reality, indicate that The Old Man exists in Eddie’s mind.

In the second instance, in the midst of a heated argument between Eddie and May, The Old Man interferes and tells a story about May's childhood. Though The Old Man speaks directly to May, she does not recognize him. Moreover, while he is telling his story, she embraces the wall and moves around the room. This shows that though she does not acknowledge him physically, she could not escape from the impact created by The Old Man's presence.

In the other four instances The Old Man tries to defend his version of story. In fact the story had two versions; one is of male dominant version projected by Eddie and The Old Man together. It is a version to subvert May's. The other is the version of May-who does not accept their version.

THE OLD MAN: (*to Eddie*) Boy, is she ever off the wall with this one. You gotta' do something about this. (53)

...

THE OLD MAN: (*to Eddie*)Stand up ! Get on yer feet now goddamit! I wanna' hear the male side a' this thing. You gotta' represent me now. Speak on my behalf. There's no one to speak *to Eddie*)Stand up ! Get on yer feet now goddamit ! I wanna' hear the male side a' this thing. You gotta' represent me now. Speak on my behalf. There's no one to speak for me now! Stand up! (*Eddie stands slowly. Stares at The Old Man*)

...

THE OLD MAN: Now tell her. Tell her the way it happened. We've got a pact. Don't forget that. (*Fool For Love*, 53 – 4)

The other one brings out female concerns by May. Whenever May brings up her version of story, The Old Man is right up there to condemn it and warns Eddie not to get hijacked by it. In all these instances, conversation takes place between Eddie and The Old Man only. The other two characters, May and Martin do not recognize him, nor acknowledge any conversation between Eddie and The Old Man. This proves that The Old Man exists in the mind of Eddie. The Old Man is not a real character like all others but exists at a different plane of reality.

Girish Karnad's Metatheatrical Exploits: An Oriental Structural Approach

Girish Karnad is one of the popular playwrights of post independent era. Like all his contemporaries he too had come under the influence of modern western dramatists. Though he follows the western dramatic tradition in terms of 'thought, content and approach', he draws the form and structure of his play directly from the folk theatres and classical theatre of India. In the words of Aparna Dharwadkar, 'Karnad employs traditional Indian narrative materials and modes of performance successfully to create a radically modern urban theatre'(355)

Karnad is highly experimental with his theatre. This is one of the features that keeps him distinct from his contemporaries. He makes use of a lot of theatrical devices or techniques that are used in the traditional and folk theatres of India. Karnad too admits this as

'the energy of folk theatre comes from the fact that although it seems to uphold traditional values, of making them literally stand on their head. The various conventions, the chorus, the masks, the seemingly unrelated cosmic episodes, the mixing of human and non-human worlds-permit the simultaneous presentations of alternative points of view, of alternative attitudes to the central problem (14).

In the play *Hayavadana* Karnad uses 'Bhagavata'- a theatrical entity of 'Yakshagana' (song of a demigod) a folk theatre form. He is intrinsically empowered with lot of theatrical powers such as introduces the theme and rhetoric of the play; introduces characters; interferes with the actors; directs the

course of action; takes ahead the debate and discourse; assumes any role he wishes to; speaks on behalf of anyone in the play; directly talks to the support staff to the play (such as musicians, chorus etc.); and directly communicates with the audience whenever he wants and with whatever the purpose be it. The range of this theatrical entity is enormous. The scope is truly 'meta'theatrical. According to Apte, the term '*Bhagavata*' is a word derived from Sanskrit which means glorious, illustrious, revered, divine, holy etc. it is an epithet applied to gods, demigods and other holy or respectable personages (709). As the very word *Bhagavata* pertains to god, he almost exercises all powers that are attributed to a god such as omnipresence, omnipotence and omniscience. *Bhagavata* is a theatrical entity endowed with the powers of god. His maneuvers within and outside the play makes him metatheatrical. In the Indian philosophy man has a permissibility to have godly powers, hence the concept '*Aham brahmasmi*' (I am the supreme spirit or creator god). It is like an anthropomorphic concept of god. *Bhagavata* possesses all the three primary functions (trinity) attributed to gods in Indian philosophy of creation, perpetuation and destruction. The whole play is his; he is inside, outside and beyond the play. He is really a metatheatrical character by the sense of the word 'meta'.

Even in the classical Sanskrit theatre, there is a theatrical entity called '*Sutradhara*'. He is similar to *Bhagavata* in folk theatre. Etymologically, *Sutradhara* is a Sanskrit word. According to Apte, it means, the thread holder; a stage manager; the principal actor who arranges the cast of characters and instructs them and takes a prominent part in the prelude (996). *Bhagavata* in *Hayavadana* does all these roles in the play. The play *Hayavadana* is modeled on the *Yakshagana*- a folk theatre form. Basically, *haya* means horse, *vadana* means face or head. In the context of this play *Hayavadana* means 'a man with a horse head'-who is a character in the play.

As an omniscient narrator, *Bhagavata* appears at anytime and anywhere. He speaks on behalf of any character. He supplies the necessary commentary to give a direction to the progress of the story and acts as a catalyst for conveying thematic concerns of the play. At the same time, he performs the role of metatheatrical character. He plays the dual role of omniscient narrator as well as a character in the play. He is also a link between the real and unreal. For the audience, he is the real character and all other characters are his (*Bhagavata*'s) creation. So *Bhagavata* is the link between the audience and the characters.

In *Hayavadana*, *Bhagavata* introduces the story and the characters after the opening prayer to *Vighneshwara* (a Hindu god with an elephant head).

BHAGAVATA : ...Our duty is merely to pay homage to the Elephant – headed god and get on with our play. This is the city of Dharmapura, ruled by king Dharmasheela whose whole fame and empire have already reached the ends of the eight directions. Two youths who dwell in this city are our heroes. One is Devadatta. Comely in appearance, fair in colour, Unrivalled in intelligence, Devadatta is the only son of the Revered Brahmin vidyasagara...

The Other youth is Kapila. He is the only son of the ironsmith Lohita, who is to the king's armoury as an axle to the chariot wheel. He is dark and plain to look at, yet in deeds which require drive and daring, in dancing, in strength and in physical skills, he has no equal. (*Hayavadana*, 1-2)

Bhagavata still expands his role in the play further. Though he is an omniscient narrator, he talks to the characters on the one hand and, identifies himself with the audience, on the other.

Bhagavata, talking to Actor, says:

Now, now, calm down! There is nothing to be afraid of here. I am here. The musicians are here. And there is our large – hearted audience. It may be that they fall asleep during a play sometimes. But they are ever alert when someone is in trouble. Now, tell us, what's the matter? (*Hayavadana*, 3)

Here, *Bhagavata*'s remarks about the audience as 'Our large-hearted audience', 'they fall asleep during a play sometimes' indicate that he is taking them into confidence and he is sensitive to the feelings

of the audience. Further, his phrase on the audience, 'they are ever alert when someone is in trouble' shows that he calls for the audience complicity in the play. When he says, 'Now, tell us', he makes himself a part of audience also. Altogether, Bhagavata operates himself at multiple levels.

First level: with the musicians (on the stage) and technicians in narrating the story to the audience.

Second level: with the actors (characters of the play) in taking the action of the play forward.

Third level: makes himself a part of audience, making 'audience complicity' possible.

Bhagavata's intervention into the action of the play can be explained through this scene. Devadatta falls in love with Padmini. Kapila goes to Padmini's house and proposes her the love of Devadatta for her. At the end of their conversation, Bhagavata enters and gives the following commentary which substitutes the action of marriage formalities and marriage between Devadatta and Padmini.

BHAGAVATHA: Need one explain to our wise and knowing audience what followed next? Padmini is the daughter of the leading merchant in Dharmapura. In her house, the very floor is swept by the Goddess of wealth. In Devadatta's house, they've the Goddess of learning for maid. What could then possibly stand in the way of bringing the families together? (Marriage music) Padmini became the better half of Devadatta and settled in his house...

[Enter Devadatta and Padmini]

(*Hayavadana*, 19)

After this commentary, Devadatta and Padmini enter (as married couple). This is probably after many days of their marriage, discussing the arrangements of a cart trip through the forest to Ujjain.

Bhagavata not only gives commentary required for filling up the gaps in action, but also speaks on behalf of the characters of the play. In *Hayavadana*, he speaks on behalf of all the three Protagonists – Devadatta, Kapila and Padmini.

After the mixing up of heads in *Kali* temple and the consequential debate over the identities, Kapila (new Kapila with Devadatta's body), distressed and agonized, retires into forest leaving Devadatta (new Devadatta with Kapila's body) and Padmini. After a long gap, Padmini carrying her son goes to forest in search of Kapila. When they meet, they engage in a conversation in which Padmini asks Kapila to explain his experiences of new life. With a great concern for Kapila's body, she asks him to tell her how his body coped up with the new environment. At that instance, instead of Kapila, Bhagavata answers on his behalf. After Bhagavata's speech, the conversation between Padmini and Kapila continues.

PADMINI: (*softly*). And how's Kapila?

[*The Bhagavata says, The following is a prose rendering of the song*]

BHAGAVATA: I spread my wings, and kicked away the earth and flew up. I covered the seven continents, the ten shores and measured the sky. Now because you have a child at your breast, a husband on your thighs, the red of rust on the lips of your late – opening mouth, I pick a picture here, and there a card of fate and live for the grace of a grain – an astrologer's bird.

KAPILA: Can I look at him?

PADMINI: That's why I brought him. (*Hayavadana*, 54–5)

In Bhagavata's speech, 'I' does not refer to him but to Kapila.

In continuation of the same conversation, Bhagavata once again interferes and speaks, this time on behalf of Padmini. This time, he talks of Padmini's agony and conflict to a query from Kapila. As he starts speaking, Padmini and Kapila freeze on the stage.

KAPILA: (*suddenly*) Why have you come away from him?

PADMINI: What do you want me to say?

[*they Freeze*]

BHAGAVATA: How could I make you understand? If Devadatta had changed overnight and had gone back to his original form, I would have forgotten you completely. But that's not how it happened. He changed day by day. Inch by Inch hair by hair. Like the trickling sand. Like the water filling the pot. And as I saw him change – I couldn't get rid of you. That's what Padmini must tell Kapila. She should say more, without concealing anything: 'Kapila, if that rishi had given me to you. Would I have gone back to Devadatta someday exactly like this? But she doesn't say anything. She remains quiet.

KAPILA: [*to Padmini*] Why have you come here?

PADMINI: I had to see you (*Hayavadana*, 56)

In Bhagavata's speech 'I' does not refer to him but to Padmini.

In both these instances, though he speaks on behalf of them, he does not speak to them directly. They do not even recognize him. Only the audience recognize him. It gives an effect that the characters of the main plot- Devadatta. Kapila and Padmini are at different planes of reality because for audience Bhagavata and his created characters-Devadatta, Kapila and Padmini are not at the same plane of reality. However, the audience recognize the sub-plot characters – Actor I, Actor II and *Hayavadana* as real characters.

There is a huge gap in the minds of the audience between the real characters (of sub-plot) and the imaginary (unreal) characters of the main plot. Bhagavata as a metatheatrical character functions as a link between the real and unreal. He interacts with the characters of his own narration five times.

- i) After the mix up of heads, Bhagavata consoles Kapila when his claim for Padmini is over ruled by the *Rishi*(a saint). (HV 41)
- ii) Speaks to Devadatta when he distributes sweets at his son's birth. (HV 45)
- iii) Speaks to Kapila before Padmini meets him along with her son in the forest. (HV 53)
- iv) Speaks to Devadatta when he comes to forest in search of Kapila. (HV 59)
- v) After the death of Devadatta and Kapila in a bloody duel, Bhagavata asks Padmini whether she needs any help.

Apart from Bhagavata, the child is the only character (a wooden doll in the main plot and a small boy in the sub-plot) who is seen in both main and sub-plots.

Bhagavata also interacts with the characters of the sub-plot. At the beginning of the play (*Hayavadana*, 2 to 11) and at the end of the play (*Hayavadana*, 64 – 71) he interacts with Actor I, Actor II and *Hayavadana* of sub-plot characters.

Thus, in *Hayavadana*, Bhagavata functions as a metatheatrical character.

Conclusion

When *Bhagavata* of *Hayavadana* and The Old Man of *Fool For Love* are compared with one another both of them are metatheatrical in their respective dramatic traditions. The Old Man is an offshoot of metatheatricality of western dramatic tradition exhibiting the features of self-dramatization, self-reference, individual consciousness and theatrical self-reference. He emerges out of the theatrical

necessity to accommodate the complexity, whereas Girish Karnad's *Bhagavata* is an offshoot of theatrical structure of the *Yakshagana* folk theatrical tradition.

The relationship between the theatrical and metatheatrical characters in *Fool For Love* is organic and cognitive whereas the relationship between them in *Hayavadana* is of structural, and of godly detachment. The metatheatricality of Girish Karnad and Sam Shepard is distinct and both these dramatists fall back on to their respective theatrical traditions. Though these characters belong to two diverse dramatic traditions, semantically, both *The Old Man* and *Bhagavata* are 'meta' in their theatricality.

Metatheatricality presents a flight from one reality to another or the characters are enabled to embrace the other. *Bhagavata* or *Sutradhara* of traditional Indian theatre can be seen as an equivalent to Metatheatrical character in the western theatrical tradition. Girish Karnad and Sam Shepard have exploited skillfully the metatheatrical character to suit their dramaturgy.

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